

Table A2. Residual diagnostics for VAR models

	France	Spain	Sweden
order of VAR model	4	5	4
autocorrelation LM test (1-4)	89.9 (0.21)	6.89 (0.98)	72.56 (0.22)
normality JB test	1.41 (0.99)	3.48 (0.90)	13.03 (0.11)
homoscedasticity White chi-sq test	312.6 (0.61)	403.2 (0.45)	21.32 (0.17)

Note: in parentheses are given p-values.